

HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

Madani Ground, Ullal-575 020 Mangluru D.K.

Ph: 0824-2461150

Ref.

Date: 23/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **ABIDA PA** from college of education Srinivas University has completed the intership of 58 days on our esteemed institution from 10/3/2021 to 31/7/2021 and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

Handwritten signature
23/08/2021
HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI
English Medium High School
Madani Ground, Ullal - 575 020

ಪಾದುವ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ (ಇಂಗ್ಲೀಷ್ ಮತ್ತು ಕನ್ನಡ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ)

ನಂತೂರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು, ದ.ಕ.-575 004

PADUA HIGH SCHOOL (ENGLISH & KANNADA MEDIUM)

Nanthuru, Mangaluru, D.K. - 575 004

Estd. : 1944

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಮಾನ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅನುದಾನದಿಂದ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದ ಕಥೋಲಿಕ್ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮಂಡಳಿಯಿಂದ ನಡೆಸಲ್ಪಡುವ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆ

DISE: 29240609801

School Code: GG0035

Email: paduaheadmaster@gmail.com

Phone: 0824 - 2211886

Mob: 8277303886

02-08-2021

To
The Dean
College of Education
Srinivas University,
Mangaluru.

Dear Sir, Madam

Mrs. Anitha Murthy student teacher of Srinivas University (College of Education) has done her internship in this school from 08-03-2021 to 23-05-2021.

We appreciate her interest and skills in Teaching, Counselling and in Educational Administration.

Thanking You,

Your's Faithfully,

Headmaster
PADUA HIGH SCHOOL
MANGALURU - 575 004, D.K.

|| Jai Gurudev ||

ODIYOOR SHREE GURUDEVA VIDYAPEETAM
Odiyoor Shree Gurudevadatta Samsthanam
(Pre Primary, Primary and High School)

P.O.: ODIYOOR-574243, Karopady Village, Bantwal Tq, D.K. Karnakata (Tulunadu)

web: www.shreeodiyoor.org

email: shreegurudevakhs@gmail.com

Tel No: 08255-266850

Mobile No: 09008276419

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Miss.Archana G.K from Srinivasa University has completed internship of 50 days in our school from 10.03.2021 to 23.07.2021. The performance was found to be Good.

PALCE : ODIYOOR

DATE : 16.08.2021

Archana G.K.
Headmaster
Shree.Gurudevada English Medium High School, Odiyoor
P.O.: Odiyoor, Karopady Village
Bantwal Tq. -574243, D. K.

BANTWA TQ DISECODE:29240106607

Email I.D:

ict2.sajipamooda@gmail.com

To whomsoever it may concern

This is certify that Mr
Arun kumar from college of
education, Srinivas University has
completed the internship of 50 days on
Our esteemed institution from 10.03.2021
to 30.04.2021 and the performance was
found to be Satisfactory .

VICE PRINCIPAL
GOVT. P. U. COLLEGE
(HIGH SCHOOL SECTION)
SAJIPAMUDA - 574 231
BANTWAL TQ, D. K

FALAH ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

K.C. Road, Vidyanagar, Talapady - 575023, Mangalore Tq. Ph: 0824- 2280036
falah_school@rediffmail.com www.falah.school.net

Ref No:.....

Date: 18-08-2021.....

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mrs: **ASHA SADASHIVAN** from **SRINIVAS COLLEGE OF EDUCATION MANGALURU** has completed the internship of **50** days in our esteemed educational institution/ school from 10-03-2021 to 27-07-2021 and the performance was found to be good.

Ajisha
HEADMISTRESS
FALAH ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL
VIDYANAGAR, TALAPADY
MANGALORE - 575 024. D. K.

GOVT PRE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

HIGH SCHOOL SECTION

KANIYOOR

5/8/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Ashalatha.P.H** from college of education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 50 days in our esteemed institution from **10-03-2021** to **20-04-2021** and from **23-06-2021** to **15-07-2021** and the performance was found to be **Good**

ಶ್ರೀಮತಿ ಅಶಲಾಧಾ ಪಿ.ಎಚ್.
ಪ್ರೌಢ ಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ
ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರೌಢ ಶಾಲೆ
ಕಾನಿಯೂರು - 574 328
ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು ಅಶಿ. ದ. ಕನ್ನಡ

SHARADA VIDYANIKETHANA PUBLIC SCHOOL
DEVINAGARA, TALAPADY, MANGALORE, D.K.

Ph. No. 0824-2280330, 2281220, 9353909330

Email.: svps@sharadagroup.in

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. ASHWITHA K**, pursuing B.Ed in Srinivas College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore is going to complete her internship of 50 days from 08th March 2021 to 15th Sept 2021.

During the aforesaid period her performance is satisfactory.

Thanks & Regards,

PRINCIPAL

Sharada Vidyanikethana Public School
Devinagara, Talapady Post, Mangalore-575 022

FALAH ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

K.C. Road, Vidyanagar, Talapady - 575023, Mangalore Tq. Ph: 0824- 2280036
falah_school@rediffmail.com www.falah.school.net

Ref No:.....

Date: 18-08-2021.....

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mrs: **AYSHA U. A** from **SRINIVAS COLLEGE OF EDUCATION MANGALURU** has completed the internship of **50** days in our esteemed educational institution/ school from 10-03-2021 to 27-07-2021 and the performance was found to be good.

HEADMISTRESS
FALAH ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL
VIDYANAGAR, TALAPADY
MANGALORE - 575 024. D. K.

ಚೈತನ್ಯ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕ್ ಸ್ಕೂಲ್
4ನೇ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕೃಷ್ಣಾಪುರ,
ಕಾಟಿಪಳ್ಳ ಪೋಸ್ಟ್ - 575 030
ಫೋನ್ 0824 - 2271080

CHAITHANYA PUBLIC SCHOOL
4th Block Krishnapura
Post Katipall - 575 030 D.K.
Ph: 0824 - 2271080

Ref.:

Date 06/08/2021

Immersion completion certificate

This is to certify that **Miss.Azreena Havva** from **Srinivas college of education** has completed the internship of **50 days** in our esteemed education institution/School from **10.03.2021 - 24.04.2021** and **12.06.2021 - 04.07.2021** and the performance was found to be good.

Signature of Headmistress
Headmistress
Chaithanya Public School
Krishnapura, Surathkal - 575 014

ದೃಢೀಕರಣ ಪತ್ರ

ಶ್ರೀನಿವಾಸ ಎಕ್ಸ್‌ಪ್ರೆಸ್‌ನಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇತರ ಯಾವುದೇ
ವಿಧ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆಯೂ ಬೇಬಿ. ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ ನಮ್ಮ ಕಾಲೇಜು
ಇಂಟರ್ ಕ್ಲಾಸ್ಟ್ ಉಪನಿರ್ದೇಶನದ ಅಧೀನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸೇರಿ
ಶಾಲಾ ಯೋಜನೆಯಡಿ ಇತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆಯೂ
ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆಯೂ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾನಿತರಾದ ಈ ಮೂಲಕ
ದೃಢೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ.

೨೨೨
ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
ವ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪಂ.ಹ.ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ
ಕರಪಾಡೆ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು

ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಎನ್. ಕೆ.ಎಸ್. 43 ದಿನ ವನ್ನು ಹಾಳೆಯಲ್ಲಿ
ಕಾಪಿ ಮಾಡಿ ಹಾಳೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆಯೂ
ಇತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆಯೂ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾನಿತರಾದ ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ದೃಢೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ.

೨೨೨
ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
ವ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪಂ.ಹ.ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ
ಕರಪಾಡೆ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು

ಕಾಸ್ಸಿಯಾ ಪ್ರೌಢ ಶಾಲೆ

ಜೆಪ್ಪು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575 001.

ಮೂರವಾಣಿ : 0824 - 2414018

School Code: GG 0043

CASCIA HIGH SCHOOL

JEPPU, MANGALURU-575 001.

Email : casciahjjeppu@yahoo.in

Dise Code: 29240611502

17.08.2021

ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ.....

ದಿನಾಂಕ.....

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Bhavya Shree** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **58** days on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021 to 10.07.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

HEADMASTER
CASCIA HIGH SCHOOL
JEPPU, MANGALORE 575001

SCHOOL REGD. NO. 0082

☎ : 2441866

KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL

Recognised by Karnataka Government

TELECOM HOUSE ROAD, MANGALORE - 575 001

E-Mail ID : ksem2013@gmail.com

23.08.2021

Ref. No. :

Date : 9

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

85419ED116

This is to certify that Miss Swinny Cardozo from college of Education, **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has completed the internship of 52 days on our esteemed institution from 15.03.2021 to 23.08.2021 and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

**KHALEEL SALAH ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL
GALIMUKA PUTTUR D.K 574313**

Email:Khaleelsalah313@Yahoo.Com

Phone:9447760000

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is certify that Mrs. Chaithralakshmi V from college of education , Srinivas University Mangalore has completed. The internship of 40 days in our esteemed educational institution /School from 15/03/2021 to 30/04/2021 and the performance was found to be Good

29/7/2021
Headmistress

Signature of head Of the
Khalil institution with seal

Galimuka Puttur, D.K. 574313

GOVERNMENT PRE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE (HIGH SCHOOL SECTION)
VIRAJPET KODAGU

28/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Miss Chandrika P K from college of Education Srinivasa
university Mangalore has completed the internship of 50 days on our esteemed
institution, offline classes from 12th march 2021 to 26th april 2021 and online
classes from 27th april 2021 to 12th may 2021 the performance was found to be
good.

S. C. K.

ಉಪ ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿ
ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪದವಿಪೂರ್ವ ಕಾಲೇಜು
ವಿರಾಜಪೇಟೆ, ಕೊಡಗು

LOURDES CENTRAL SCHOOL

Bijai Church Campus, Bijai, Mangaluru - 575 004.
Affiliated to the Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi.
Affiliation No. : 830120

Ph : 0824 - 2223366, 2213865 (O)

Manager : 0824 - 4276588

E-mail : principal@lourdescentralschool.com

Website : www.lourdescentralschool.com

Date: 18.08.2021

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms CLAVIA LEWIS from Srinivas University, college of Education, Mangalore has completed the Internship of 100 days in our esteemed educational institution from 13/03/2021 to 25/08/2021 and her performance was found excellent and satisfactory.

We wish her all the best in her future endeavours

Rev Fr Robert D Souza

Principal

**Lourdes Central School
Bijai, Mangaluru - 575 004**

Nithyadar Eng Med School

ನಿತ್ಯಾದರ್ ಆಂಗ್ಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಶಾಲೆ

School Dis: 29240607637

Nithyadar Nagar,
Permanner Post,
Mangalore - 575 017.

Ph: 0824- 2460394

Date: 23/08/21.

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

35 + 42 = 77 days

This is to certify that Ms. Deeksha from College of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 35 days in our institution from 12/03/2021 to 28/04/2021 and the performance was found to be very good.

Pravind
HEADMSTRESS
NITHYADAR ENG MED SCHOOL
NITHYADAR NAGAR, PERMANNUR
MANGALORE - 575 017

ಕಾಸ್ಸಿಯಾ ಪ್ರೌಢ ಶಾಲೆ

ಜೆಪ್ಪು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575 001.

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : 0824 - 2414018

School Code: GG 0043

CASCIA HIGH SCHOOL

JEPPU, MANGALURU-575 001.

Email : casciahjjeppu@yahoo.in

Dise Code: 29240611502

ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ.....

ದಿನಾಂಕ.....17.08.2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Deekshitha D Souza** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **58** days on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021 to 10.07.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

HEADMASTER
CASCIA HIGH SCHOOL
JEPPU, MANGALORE 575001

Phone : 0824-2462919

ST SEBASTIAN ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

PERMANNUR, MANGALORE - 575 017.

(UNDER THE MANAGEMENT OF THE CATHOLIC BOARD OF EDUCATION MANGALORE)

Ref. No.

Date :

16/08/2021

TO WHMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Deekshitha** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **55** days on our esteemed institution from **12/03/2021** to **06/08/2021** and performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Headmistress

ST SEBASTIAN ENGLISH
MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL
PERMANNUR - 575 017
MANGALORE, D.K.

Phone : 0824 - 2463922

UNAIDED
ST. JOSEPH'S JOYLAND HIGH SCHOOL
(ENGLISH MEDIUM)

KOLYA, SOMESHWAR, MANGALORE - 575 022. D. K.
(Managed by : Kolya Education Society [R.] Mangalore.)

Ref. No.

Date 23-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Dexitha Crasta** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 50 days on our esteemed institution from 10.03.2021 to 07.08.2021 and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Admission
Unaided St. Joseph's Joyland
English Medium School
Kolya Someshwar Mangalore. D.K.

JANATHA HIGHER PRIMARY ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL

ADYANADKA ,KEPU,BANTWALA TALUKU-574260

School Dis - 29240103612

Adyanadka Educational Society Reg.

Date. 23/08/2021

TO WHOM SOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

**This is to certify that DHANYA V. RAI from college of
Education Srinivas University has completed the internship of 62
Days on our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 15-08-2021
And the performance was found to be very good.**

Headmaster
Janatha Higher Primary
English Medium School
Adyanadka, Bantwal Tq. - 574 260, D.K.

**KAMIL ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL
KOKKECHAL**

KAYYAR POST, UPPALA VIA, KASARAGOD-671322

Date: 30-06-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms Fathimath Inthiyasunisa** from college of education, **Shrinivas University** has completed the internship of **76** days esteemed institution from **15-03-2021** to **30-06-2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**

PRINCIPAL
KAMIL ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL
Kokkechal, (Recognized. by Govt. of Kerala)
P.O.Kayyar, VIA-Uppala-671322

LOURDES CENTRAL SCHOOL

Bijai Church Campus, Bijai, Mangaluru - 575 004.
Affiliated to the Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi.
Affiliation No. : 830120
Ph : 0824 - 2223366, 2213865 (O)
Manager : 0824 - 4276588
E-mail : principal@lourdescentralschool.com
Website : www.lourdescentralschool.com

Date: 18.08.2021

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms GAYATHRI M from Srinivas University, college of Education, Mangalore has completed the Internship of 60 days in our esteemed educational institution from 13/03/2021 to 25/08/2021 and her performance was found excellent and satisfactory.

We wish her all the best in her future endeavours

Rev Fr Robert D Souza
Principal
Lourdes Central School
Bijai, Mangaluru - 575 004

Sri Chaitanya Techno School

(Affiliated to CBSE, NEW DELHI)

Kottara Chowki, Bangra Kulur Road, Mangaluru-575 013

Affiliation No: 830850
Mobile : 9071766556

05-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **MS.GAYATHRI** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 100 days on our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 14-08-2021 and the performance was found to be good.

Rajpal
15/8/2021
PRINCIPAL

SRI CHAITANYA TECHNO SCHOOL
KOTTARA CHOWKI, MANGALORE - 05

KUMARASWAMY VIDYALAYA

Sponsored by : ANUGRAHA EDUCATION TRUST (R.)
VIDYANAGARA - SUBRAHMANYA, SULLIA, T.Q., D.K. 574 238

(Recognised by Govt. of Karnataka)

Ph : 08257 - 281247 (O)
281515 (R)

Smt. Vidyaratna H. M.Sc., B.Ed.
Principal

School Code : GG0313

DISE CODE : 29240503501 (Primary), 29240503507 (High School)

Ref. _____

Date: 06.08.2021

TO whomsoever if may concern

This is to certify that Miss. Geetha D. from College of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 70 days in our esteemed institution from 10.03.2021 to 06.08.2021 and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

HEADMISTRESS

Kumaraswamy English Medium High School
Subrahmanya, Sullia Tq, D.K. - 574 238

Thouheed English Medium School

Dise Code : 29240109002

Lower Bazar, Bantwal - 574 211. D. K. Karnataka, South India Phone : 08255-232329, 234329
e-mail : thouheedbantwal05@gmail.com web : bantwalthouheed-edu.in

Date: 12-08-2021

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. Greshal Préma Baretto from Srinivas University College of Education, Srinivas University Pandeshwar Mangalore, has successfully completed the internship of 50 days in Thouheed English Medium School and the performance was found to be good.

Headmistress

Thouheed English Medium High School
Lower Bazar, Bantwal
Headmistress

Thouheed English Medium School

*GOVT PRE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
HIGH SCHOOL SECTION
KANIYOOR*

5/8/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Gunavathi.N.R** from college of education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 50 days in our esteemed institution from **10-03-2021** to **20-04-2021** and from **23-06-2021** to **15-07-2021** and the performance was found to be **Good**

കരിയ പ്രീ-യൂണിവേഴ്സി കോളേജ്
പ്രൊഫ. അനാ. പി.എസ്.
ഇന്റേണൽ ടീച്ചിംഗ് ഓഫീസ്
കാനിയൂർ - 574 328
ഇ.എസ്.എസ്. അ. ടി. കെ.എസ്.

Phone : 2230460

SACRED HEARTS' HR. PRY. (ENGLISH MEDIUM) SCHOOL

Kulshekar, Mangaluru - 575 005

(The Bethany Educational Society (R) Mangalore)

(ಬೆಥನಿ ಎಜುಕೇಶನಲ್ ಸೊಸೈಟಿ (ರಿ) ಮಂಗಳೂರು)

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mrs. Hafsha Banu** from college of Education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **45 days** in our esteemed Institution from **10.03.2021 to 17.07.2021**.

She has very good communicative skills and excellent in her teaching methods. She has performed all her duties systematically and efficiently during her tenure.

Date: 06.08.2021

Place : Kulshekar

For Sr. Lavitha

Headmistress

SACRED HEARTS' HR.PRY. SCHOOL

(English-Medium)

KULSHEKAR, MANGALURU - 575005

D.K.Z.P HIGHER PRIMARY SCHOOL

KALLADKA, BANTWAL TALUK-574222

Gmail:gupskalladka@gmail.com

Date: 26-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER MAY CONCERN

85U19ED133

This is to certify that **Miss Hemavathi** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 42 days on our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 08-04-2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

GRADUATE HEAD MASTER
DKZP Model H.P. School, Kalladka
Bantwal Taluk, D. K.

2987864
Phone : 2495863.

SRI RAMAKRISHNA HIGH SCHOOL
(ENGLISH MEDIUM) S.R.S.HOME, MANGALURU - 575 003.
Email : srsbuntshostel@rediffmail.com

Ref :

Date ..18/8/21.....

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mrs.INDUSHREE from college of Education SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY has completed the internship of 60 days in our esteemed institution from 12.03.2021 to 11.08.2021 and the performance was found to be very good.

[Signature]
Headmistress
SRI RAMAKRISHNA HIGH SCHOOL,
SRS Home, MANGALORE - 575 003

Name : Indushree.

No of days Present - 60 days.

VIDYARASHMI VIDYALAYA

VIDYAGANGOTHRI, SAVANOR, PUTTUR Tq., D. K., Karnataka - 574 202

Phone : (08251) 282061 | 282396

E-mail : svrv85@yahoo.in

Website : www.vidyashmi.in

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

CERTIFICATE

85UFGED136

This is to certify that Ms. JAYASHREE B., D/o Mr. Venkappa Naika, a B.Ed. student of Srinivas College of Education, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has completed the internship of 40 days in our school between 10 March 2021 and 6 May 2021.

During the above period her services and performances were good.

27 August 2021.

[Handwritten signature]
27/8/2021

Headmaster
Vidyashmi Vidyalaya
(English Medium)
Savanor, Puttur D.K. 574 202
DISE CODE : 29240406206

DKZP MODEL HIGHER PRIMARY SCHOOL

CHELAIRU, MANGALORE-574146

18.08.2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MY CONCERN

This is certify that **Mr. Jayashree.S** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **70** days on our school from **10.04.2021** to **18.08.2021** and the performance was found to be **Good**.

Chelairu

18-08-2021

Ye

ಪದವೀಧರರೇಷಗ ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯ
ದ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪಂ. ಮಾದರಿ ಹಿರಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆ
ಚೆಲೈರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 574 146

KAMIL ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL

KOKACHAL, KAYYAR POST, KASARAGOD, 671322

Date 13/8/2021

TOWHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Mrs. K MARIYAMBI RAMSEENA From College of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 90 days on our esteemed Institution from 17/2/2021 to 9/8/2021 and performance was formed to be satisfactory .

PRINCIPAL
KAMIL ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL
Kokkechal, (Recognized. by Govt. of Kerala)
P.O.Kayyar, VIA-Uppala-671322

☎ : 08262-235976

ಸಂತ ಜೋಸೆಫ್ ಕಾನ್ವೆಂಟ್ ಬಾಲಕಿಯರ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ

ಚರ್ಚ್ ರಸ್ತೆ, ಚಿಕ್ಕಮಗಳೂರು - 577 101.

St. Joseph's Convent Girls' High School

Church Street, Chikmagalur - 577 101.

Dise Code : 29170624106

Ref. No. : _____

Date : _____

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms Kavya M S from Shrinivas University College of Education, Pandeshwar Manglore has completed the intership of 100 days in our esteemed educational institution from 07/09/2020 to 03/01/2021 and the performance was found to be good.

Seffurkado
Headmistress
St. Joseph's Convent
Girls High School,
Chikmagalur.

You are the Light of the World

KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL

TELECOM HOUSE ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001
DISE Code: 29240610708

☎: 2441866
Mob : 8722964438

19.08.2021

Date :

Ref. No. :

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **mrs. KIRAN KUMARI SHAW** from college of Education, **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has completed the internship of **45 days** on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021 to 19.08.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory.**

Headmistress
KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL
OLD KENT ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001

**D.K. Z.P.H.P. SCHOOL, VALACHILL
P.O FARANGIPETE, MANGALURU TALUK- 574143**

31.08.2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Kulashree K.M** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **80** days on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021** to **31.08.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Apnaya ras

ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರ.
ದ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪಿ.ಹಿ.ಪ್ರಾ.ಶಾಲೆ
ಬೆಳ್ಳೆಲ್, P.O:ಫರಂಗಿಪೇಟೆ
ಮಂಗಳೂರು ತಾಲೂಕು-574143

D.K.Z.P HIGHER PRIMARY SCHOOL

KALLADKA, BANTWAL TALUK-574222

Gmail:gupskalladka@gmail.com

Date: 31/08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER MAY CONCERN

85U19ED141

This is to certify that **Miss Latha** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 42 days on our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 08-04-2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

LATHA

85U19ED141

GRADUATE HEAD MASTER
DKZP Model H.P. School, Kalladka
Bantwal Taluk, D. K.

Elpis English School
Shantipur, Penchartal
Unakoti
Tripura- 799 263

To,
The Dean
Srinivas University,
College of Education
Mangalore- 575 001

CERTIFICATE ON COMPLETION OF SCHOOL INTERNSHIP

1. This is to certify that **Mrs. Lopa Dewan**, has completed **90 days** of her School Internship Training period successfully from **07 April 2021 to 27 Jul 2021** as a part of **Bachelor of Education** Programme. As per the records, she is pursuing the **Bachelor of Education** degree from **Srinivas University, College of Education, Mangalore**.

2. This certificate is issued on the basis of attendance register maintained in our Institution for the above said period.

Signature of Headmaster

Headmaster
ELPIS ENGLISH SCHOOL
Pecharthal : Tripura.

ದೃಢೀಕರಣ ಪತ್ರ

ಮಂಜುಳ, ಎನ್ಯಾನ್ಸಿ ಶೆಟ್ಟಿ, ಶ್ರೀನಿವಾಸ
ಯುನಿವರ್ಸಿಟಿ B.Ed ಎನ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಇವರು
ದಿನಾಂಕ 10/03/2021 ರಿಂದ 19/07/2021
ರವರೆಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆ (ದ-ಕ-ಜಿ. ಪಂ. ಬನ್ನೇತ
ಹಿ. ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ ಕೆಎಂಜಿ) ಇಲ್ಲಿ internship
ಇನ್ನೂ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆಯೆಂದು, ಈ ಇವರು
ಬತ್ತೆ ಮತ್ತು ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತರಬೇತಿ ಮಾಡಿ, ಪಠ್ಯಕ್ರಮ
ಜೈವವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಕುರಿತು ತನ್ನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆಯೆಂದು ಈ
ವಿಷಯ ದೃಢೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

ಕೆಎಂಜಿ
06/08/2021

Su__i
Dr. K. B. P. L. K. Prasad, K. M. J. S.
ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು - 574 202, ಪುತ್ತೂರು, ದ. ಕ.
DISE CODE: 29240403201

Ph : 04994 - 225757
E-mail : slvksd@gmail.com

SHREE LAKSHMI VENKATESH VIDYALAYA

[A unit of Shree Lakshmi Venkatesh Trust (R.)]

Affiliated to Bharatheeya Vidya Nikethan, Kerala

NIOS Accreditation No. OBO914016 Affiliation No. 1441

DWARAKA NAGAR, KASARAGOD - 671 121

Ref.....

Date 17-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms Melita Jesma Crasta** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 100 days (50 days of online & 50 days of offline) on our esteemed institution and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

K. Salayakshi
17/8/2021
Headmistress
Shree Lakshmi Venkatesh Vidyalaya
NIOS Accreditation No: OBO914016
Dwaraka Nagar, AT Road, Kasaragod-671 121

ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆ 1991

ನೂರುಲ್ ಹುದಾ ಅಂಗ್ಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಹಿಲಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆ

2ನೇ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕಾಟಿಪಳ್ಳ - 575 030, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಉತ್ತರ - ದ.ಕ.

(ಸಂಸ್ಥಾಪನೆ - ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆ : ನೂರುಲ್ ಹುದಾ ಎಜ್ಯುಕೇಶನ್ ಟ್ರಸ್ಟ್ (ರಿ.) ಕಾಟಿಪಳ್ಳ)

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : (0824) 2270804, Email : nhet89katipalla@live.com

ಶಾಲಾ ಡೈಸ್ ಸಂಕೇತ : 29240607903

Ref :

ದಿನಾಂಕ :

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms.Mufeedath from Srinivas University College of Education, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has completed the Internship of 50 days in our esteemed Educational Institution/school from 10/03/2021 to 05/08/2021 and the performance was found to be Good/Satisfactory.

Headmistress
NOORUL HUDA ENG. MED. HIGH SCHOOL
II BLOCK, KATIPALLA - 575 030
MANGALORE NORTH

Signature of Head Master/Mistress

**D.K.Z.P.H.P SCHOOL, BOLAR
P.O. BOLAR. MANGALORE TALUK 575001**

12-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

SSU19ED146

This is to Certify that Ms. Nausheera from college of education. Srinivas University has completed the internship of 80 days on our esteemed institution from 15.03.2021 to 12.08.2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

ವಾಣಿಜ್ಯನಾಥಯ್ಯರು
ದ.ಕ. ಜಿ.ಪಂ. ಒ.ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ
ಬೋಲಾರ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575001

ಸಂತ ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಾ ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ

ಫಿಲೋನಗರ, ಅಂಚೆ : ದರ್ಬೆ 574202, ಪುತ್ತೂರು, ದ.ಕ.

ಮಾನ್ಯತೆ ಆದೇಶ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ : D3/ARR/23/2019-20 DATED 20-11-2019

ಉಪನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು (ಆಡಳಿತ) ಸಾ. ಶಿ. ಇಲಾಖೆ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು 08251 230470

ಫೋನ್.ಕೋಡ್: 29240408703

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. NAVYA M** from college of education, **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has completed the internship of **70 days** on our esteemed institution from **12-03-2021 to 30-08-2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Place: Puttur
Date: 31/08/2021

Leonilla Vargas

Headmistress

ಸಂತ ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಾ ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ

ಫಿಲೋನಗರ, ದರ್ಬೆ ಅಂಚೆ, ಪುತ್ತೂರು

ದ ಕ. 574 202, Ph: 230470

سہارا

Sahara English Medium School

Addoor, Mangalore, D.K. - 574 145 ☎: 2266936

Ref:

Date: 23/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This Is To Certify That Ms Nishmitha From College Of Education, Srinivas University Has Completed The Internship Of 49 Days in Our Esteemed Institution, Sahara English Medium Higher Primary And High School Addoor, From 12/03/2021 To 22/07/2021 And The Performance Was Found To Be Satisfactory.

Headmaster

SAHARA ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGHER
PRIMARY AND HIGH SCHOOL
ADDOOR, MANGALURU - 574 145

ಉಪಪ್ರಾಶುಪಾಲರ ಕಛೇರಿ

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕ್ ಸ್ಕೂಲ್ ಬೆಳ್ಳಾರೆ ಸುಳ್ಯ ತಾಲೂಕು ದ.ಕ. 574212

KARNATAKA PUBLIC SCHOOL BELLARE , SULLIA TALUK D.K

ಇಮೇಲ್: gpucbellare51@yahoo.co.in , kpsbellare@gmail.com

ದೂರವಾಣಿ: 08257-272336,

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. **PALLAVI K** from **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF EDUCATION MANGALORE** has completed the internship of 50 days in our esteemed education institution from **10-03-2021** to **07-08-2021** and the performance was found to be **GOOD**

DATE : 07-08-2021

ಉಪಪ್ರಾಶುಪಾಲರು
ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕ್ ಸ್ಕೂಲ್, ಬೆಳ್ಳಾರೆ
ಸುಳ್ಯ ತಾಲೂಕು, ದ.ಕ-574212

Govt. High school Kurnad

Bantwal Taluk Dakshina Kannada
karantaka-574153

18.08.2021

To whomsoever it may concern

This is to certify that **Mrs Pavithra k** from College of education,
Srinivas University has completed the internship of 50 days on our esteemed
institution from **12.03.2021** to **14.05.2021** and the performance was found to
be **satisfactory**.

18/08/2021
ಶ್ರೀಮತಿ ಪಾವಿತ್ರಾ ಕುಮಾರ್
ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪದವಿಪೂರ್ವ ಕಾಲೇಜು
ಕುರ್ನಾಡು, ಬಂಟ್ವಾಳ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು, ದ.ಕ

Sl No of Working Days	Date	Signature
9	22/3/2021	by [Signature]
10	23/3/2021	by [Signature]
11	24/3/2021	by [Signature]
12	25/3/2021	by [Signature]
13	26/3/2021	by [Signature]
14	27/3/2021	by [Signature]
15	28/3/2021	by [Signature]
Signature of HM.		by [Signature] 29/3/21

Sl No of Working Days	Date	Signature
16.	29/3/2021	by [Signature] (Half day)
17	30/3/2021	by [Signature]
18	31/3/2021	by [Signature]
19	01/04/2021	by [Signature]
20	02/04/2021	Holiday
21	03/04/2021	by [Signature]
22.	Signature of HM.	by [Signature] 05/4/2021

Sl No of Working Days-	Date	Signature
22	05/04/2021	Bayan
23	06/04/2021	Bayan
24	07/04/2021	Bayan
25	08/04/2021	Bayan
26	09/04/2021	Bayan
27	10/04/2021	Holiday.
	Signature of HM.	He 09/04/2021

VIVEKANANDA ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL

[A UNIT VIVEKANANDA VIDYAVARDHAKA SANGHA, PUTTUR (R)]

VIVEKANAGARA, THENKILA, PUTTUR -574201.

Phone no: 08251-232015, Website: www.vems.vivekanandaedu.org,

E-mail -school.vem@gmail.com, DISE CODE: 29240408104

Date: 23-08-2021

TO WHOM SO EVER IT CONCERN

This Is To Certify That Mr. Prabhakara S from Shrinivas University, Mangalore has completed the internship of 60days on our esteemed institution from 19-03-2021 to 30-06-2021 and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

HEADMASTER
vivekananda English Medium
High School
VIVEKA NAGAR
PUTTUR 574 201

St. Rita English Medium High School

Jeppu, Mangalore - 575 001.

Phone : 0824 - 2415002

Ref. No. :

Date:

31-07-2021

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mrs. Prajitha Shetty J. from Srinivas University Pandeshwar Mangaluru, has successfully completed the Internship of 35 days in our school from 10-03-2021 to 26-04-2021 and the performance was found to be good.

Headmistress
St. Rita English High School
Cascia, Jeppu, Mangaluru

St. Ann's Composite PU College

Opp. Head Post Office

Pandeshwar, Mangalore -1

Certificate of Completion of School Internship

This is to certify that Ms. Pranitha Juliana Pinto, has completed 82 Days of her School Internship Training period successfully from 06 - 03- 2021 to 20- 7- 2021 .

The above certificate is issued based on the attendance register maintained in our College during the above period.

Signature of the Principal

PRINCIPAL
ST ANN'S P.U.COLLEGE
MANGALORE -575001

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರ
ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಇಲಾಖೆ

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ.ಪೂ.ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕಬಕ, ಪುತ್ತೂರುತಾ, ದ.ಕ.ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ

ಇಮೇಲ್‌ಇಠಾಸ:ghskabaka@yahoo.com

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : 0825128118

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mrs. Prathibha.G from college of education Srinivas University has completed the internship of 63 days on our esteemed institution from 15.03.2021 to 27.07.2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

DATE:13.07.2021

PLACE: KABAKA

ಹರಿಯ ಪದವೀಧರ ಸಹಾಯಕ
ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪದವಿ ಪೂರ್ವ ಕಾಲೇಜು
ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕಬಕ
ಪುತ್ತೂರು, ದ. ಕ. 574 220

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION**

ATTENDANCE SHEET FOR INTERNSHIP STUDENTS

NAME OF THE STUDENT: *Prathima K B. Ed (4 Sem)*

NAME OF THE SCHOOL: *ಶಿಶು ವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ ಶಿವಮೊಗ್ಗ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕಚೇರಿ (ಮೊದಲ ಹಂತ)*

Sl. No. of working days	DATE	SIGNATURE	Sl. No. of working days	DATE	SIGNATURE
	12/03/2021			09/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	13/03/2021			10/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	14/03/2021			Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>
	15/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		11/04/2021	
	16/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		12/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	17/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		13/04/2021	<i>holiday</i>
	18/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		14/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	19/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		15/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	20/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		16/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>		17/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	21/03/2021			Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>
	22/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		18/04/2021	
	23/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		19/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	24/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		20/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	25/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		21/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	26/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		22/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	27/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		23/04/2021	<i>word</i>
	Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>		24/04/2021	<i>word</i>
	28/03/2021			Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>
	29/03/2021	-		25/04/2021	
	30/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		26/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	31/03/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		27/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	01/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		28/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	02/04/2021	<i>holiday</i>		29/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	03/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>		30/04/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>		01/05/2021	<i>Prathima</i>
	04/04/2021			Signature of the H M	<i>[Signature]</i>

05/04/2021 Prathima
06/04/2021 -
07/04/2021 Prathima
08/04/2021 Prathima

	05/04/2021				
	06/04/2021				
	07/04/2021				
	08/04/2021				

Please note: The above format has to be prepared by each students to maintain the attendance at the internship school with the signature of the H M at the end of every week and school seal must be there on each attendance sheet. Kindly put the serial number depending on the number of working days.

Sri Chaitanya Techno School

(Affiliated to CBSE, NEW DELHI)

Kottara Chowki, Bangra Kulur Road, Mangaluru-575 013

Affiliation No: 830850
Mobile : 9071766556

05-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Preethesh** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 100 days on our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 14-08-2021 and the performance was found to be good.

Raspa

PRINCIPAL
PRINCIPAL

SRI CHAITANYA TECHNO SCHOOL
KOTTARA CHOWKI, MANGALORE - 06

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರ

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪದವಿ ಪೂರ್ವ ಕಾಲೇಜು (ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ) ಸಾಣೂರು-574114
ಫೋನ್:9449664635 ಶಾಲಾ ಮೇಲ್ ಐ.ಡಿ:gpucsanoorh@gmail.com

To Whomsoever it may concern.

85u19ED157-

This is to certify that MS.Prema Sangeetha D'souza from college of education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 50 days on our esteemed institution 10.03.2021 to 30.04.2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

ಹಿರಿಯ ಸಹಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು
ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪದವಿ ಪೂರ್ವ ಕಾಲೇಜು
(ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ) ಸಾಣೂರು
ಕಾರ್ಕಳ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಉಡುಪಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ

DKZP MODEL HIGHER PRIMARY SCHOOL

CHELAIRU, MANGALORE-574146

18. 8.2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MY CONCERN

This is certify that **Mr. Prithvi R** from college of education,
Srinivas University has completed the internship of **70** days on our
school from **10.04.2021** to **18. 8.2021** and the performance was found to
be **Good**.

Chelairu

18. 08. 2021

ಪದವೀಧರಣೆಗೆ ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
ದ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪಂ. ಮಾದರಿ ಹಿರಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆ
ಚಿಲೈರು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 574 146

ದ.ಕ. ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ಹಿಲಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆ

ಕೊಕ್ಕುಡೆ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 574 146, ಉತ್ತರ ವಲಯ

ಕ್ರಮಾಂಕ.....

ದಿನಾಂಕ: ೦೩-೦೩-೨೦೨೧

ಕುಮಾರಿ ರಂಜನಿಯವರು ಬಿ.ಕೆ.ಬಿ.ವಿ.ಪ್ರಿ ಶಾಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ

10/3/2021 ರಿಂದ 08/04/2021 ರವರೆಗೆ Internship

course ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿ ಕರವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಮೂಲಕ

ವೃತ್ತಿ ಕರವಾಗಿ.

ಸ್ಥಳ:- ಕೊಕ್ಕುಡೆ

Jahanside
ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
ದ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪಂ.ಹಿ.ಪ್ರಾ.ಶಾಲೆ, ಕೊಕ್ಕುಡೆ
ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಉತ್ತರವಲಯ,
ಅಂಚೆ:ಕೊಕ್ಕುಡೆ-574146

Phone : 0824-2462919

ST SEBASTIAN ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

PERMANNUR, MANGALORE - 575 017.

(UNDER THE MANAGEMENT OF THE CATHOLIC BOARD OF EDUCATION MANGALORE)

Ref. No.

Date :

16/08/2021

TO WHMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mrs. Rashmi Kumari** from college of education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 55 days on our esteemed institution from **12/03/2021** to **06/08/2021** and performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Headmistress
ST SEBASTIAN ENGLISH
MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL
PERMANNUR - 575 017
MANGALORE, D.K.

ಸಂತ ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಾ ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ

ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಗರ, ಅಂಚೆ : ದರ್ಬೆ 574202, ಪುತ್ತೂರು, ದ.ಕ.

ಮಾನ್ಯತೆ ಆದೇಶ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ : D3/ARR/23/2019-20 DATED 20-11-2019

ಉಪನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು (ಆಡಳಿತ) ಸಾ. ಶಿ. ಇಲಾಖೆ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು 08251 230470

ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್.ನೋಡ್: 29240408703

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

BSU19ED162

This is to certify that **Ms. Renita Galbao** from college of education, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY has completed the internship of ~~70~~ days on our esteemed institution from **12-03-2021 to 30-08-2021** and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

Leonilla Veigas

Headmistress

ಸಂತ ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಾ ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ

ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಗರ, ದರ್ಬೆ ಅಂಚೆ, ಪುತ್ತೂರು

ದ.ಕ. 574 202, Ph: 230470

Place: Puttur

Date: 31/08/2021

☎: 2441866
Mob : 8722964438

KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL

TELECOM HOUSE ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001
DISE Code: 29240610708

4.08.2021

Ref. No. :

Date :

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Roohee** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of **64** days on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021** to **31.07.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Headmistress
KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL
OLD KENT ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001

MOULANA AZAD MODEL SCHOOL

GURUKAMBALA, KINNIKAMBALA

MANGALORE DAKSHINAKANNADA

TO WHOMSOEVER ITMAY CONCERN

83419ED165

This is to certify that Ms.Samreen from college of Education, Srinivasa University has completed the internship of 80 days on our esteemed institution from 10-mar-2021 to 21-Aug-2021 and the performance was found to be SATISFACTORY.

Head Master

ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
ಕೌಲಾನ ಆಜಾದ್ ಮಾದರಿ ಶಾಲೆ
ಗುರುಕಂಬಳ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು 574 151

ಮಿಲಾಗ್ರಿಸ್ ಪದವಿಪೂರ್ವಕಾಲೇಜು

(ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ) ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575 001 (ದ.ಕ.)

MILAGRES PRE- UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
(High School Section) MANGALORE - 575001 (D.K.)

ದೂರವಾಣಿ Phone : 0824 - 2425175

Date: 17-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Miss. SANGEETHA DSOUZA from College of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 50 days in our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 26-04-2021 and from 26-07-2021 to 16-08-2021. Her performance was found to be good.

Signature

VICE PRINCIPAL
MILAGRES PRE-UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
MANGALORE - 575 001

Place : Mangaluru

Date : 17-08-2021

SHARADA VIDYANIKETHANA PUBLIC SCHOOL
DEVINAGARA, TALAPADY, MANGALORE, D.K.

Ph. No. 0824-2280330, 2281220, 9353909330

Email.: svps@sharadagroup.in

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. SANJANA JAYARAM TALAPADY**, pursuing B.Ed in Srinivas College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore is going to complete her internship of 50 days from 08th March 2021 to 15th Sept 2021.

During the aforesaid period her performance is satisfactory.

Thanks & Regards,

PRINCIPAL

PRINCIPAL

Sharada Vidyanikethana Public School
Devinagara, Talapady Post, Mangalore-575022

Ph : 04994 - 225757
E-mail : slvksd@gmail.com

SHREE LAKSHMI VENKATESH VIDYALAYA

[A unit of Shree Lakshmi Venkatesh Trust (R.)]

Affiliated to Bharatheeya Vidya Nikethan, Kerala

NIOS Accreditation No. OBO914016 Affiliation No. 1441

DWARAKA NAGAR, KASARAGOD - 671 121

17-08-2021
Date :

Ref:

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms Sanusha. S** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 100 days (50 days of online & 50 days of offline) on our esteemed institution and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

K. Kalajabshi
17/8/2021

Headmistress
Shree Lakshmi Venkatesh Vidyalaya
NIOS Accreditation No: OBO914016
Dwaraka Nagar, AT Road, Kasaragod-671 121

HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

Madani Ground, Ullal-575 020 Mangluru D.K.

Ph: 0824-2461150

Ref.

Date: 23/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **SHARANYA KS** from college of education Srinivas University has completed the intership of 58 days on our esteemed institution from 10/3/2021 to 31/7/2021 and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

Headmaster
23/08/2021
HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI
English Medium High School
Madani Ground, Ullal - 575 020

TAALEEM EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY'S POSH ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL

Govt. Recog

MAS Building, Colmorod, Navelim, Salcete - Goa. 403 707
Phone: 8605652047, Email: sashakoorschool@yahoo.com

Regd. No.F/431/09-31383, National Commission for Minority Edu.Inst., Govt. of India, Delhi.
School Index No. 08.66 (Goa Board)

Date: 05th August 2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Miss Sharma Mamta**, 2nd Year B.Ed trainee of Srinivas University College of Education Mangaluru, has completed her internship training for 34 days in our School and her performance was found to be satisfactory.

Wishing her Good luck and success in her future endeavours.

Dr. S. A. Shakoor
Manager

Posh English High School
Navelim, Salcete-Goa

Phone: 0824-24664498

UNAIDED BHARATHI ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

ಅನುದಾನರಹಿತ ಭಾರತಿ ಆಂಗ್ಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪ್ರೌಢ ಶಾಲೆ

MASTHIKATTE, P.O. ULLAL, MANGALORE TALUK, PIN - 575 020.

ಮಾಸ್ತಿಕಟ್ಟೆ, ಅಂಚೆ ಉಳ್ಳಾಲ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ತಾಲೂಕು - 575020.

Dakshina Kannada ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ

Ref. No - 05/BEM/2021-22
(ಉಲ್ಲೇಖ ವಂಚು)

Date: 24.08.2021
(ತಾರೀಖು)

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

THIS IS TO BE CERTIFY THAT MS SHAVINA BS FROM COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HAS COMPLETED THE INTERNSHIP OF 40 DAYS ON OUR
ESTEEMED INSTITUTION FROM 10/03/2021 TO 24/04/2021 AND THE PERFORMANCE
WAS FOUND TO BE SATISFACTORY.

Principal
UNAIDED BHARATHI ENG. MED. PKY. & HIGH SCHOOL
MASTIKATTE, ULLALA 575020
PH: 0824-2464498

ಸ. ಪ. ಪೂ. ಕಾಲೇಜು ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ ಕುಂಬ್ರ

ಪುತ್ತೂರು ತಾಲೂಕು ದ. ಕ. 574210

ದೂ. ಸಂ. 08251 - 285080

ಫೈಸ್ ನಂ. 29240406707

ಉಲ್ಲೇಖ :

ದಿನಾಂಕ 25.08.2021

ಶ್ರೀನಿವಾಸ ಕಾಲೇಜು ಆಫ್ ಎಜುಕೇಶನ್ ಇಲ್ಟಿ ಬಿ.ಐ.ಡಿ
 ತರಬೇತಿ ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಕುಮಾರಿ ಶ್ರೀಮಯಾ ಎಂ.ಎಂ.ಎಂ.ಎಂ.ಎಂ.
 ದಿನಾಂಕ 10.03.2021 ರಿಂದ 08.08.2021 ರವರೆಗೆ
 ನಮ್ಮ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಯಾಗಿ 55 ದಿನಗಳ ಕಾಲ ಇಂಟರ್‌ಮೀಡಿಯೇಟ್ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ
 ಕೈಗೊಂಡು ಕಡತವು ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವಂತೆ ಈಗಾಗಲೇ ಅವಳು
 ಅನಂತ ಅಂತರ ಪ್ರವಚನಗಳನ್ನು ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವಂತೆ
 ವೃತ್ತಿಪರವಾಗಿ

ಸ್ಥಳ : ಕುಂಬ್ರ

(Signature)
 ಹಿರಿಯ ಪದವಿಧಾರ ಸಹಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು
 ಸ.ಪ.ಪೂ.ಕಾ. ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ
 ಕುಂಬ್ರ, ಪುತ್ತೂರು - 574 210
 ಫೈಸ್ ನಂ. : 29240406707

GURUKULA PUBLIC SCHOOL

Bhandya Educational Trust (R)

Affiliation No. 830186

(Affiliated to Central Board of Secondary Education, New Delhi)

School No. - 41056

Ref. No. : 2213/21-22

Date : 14/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Shruthi from College of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 100 days in our institution from 15/03/2021 to 03/08/2021 and the performance was found to be very good.

Principal

GURUKULA PUBLIC SCHOOL
Bhandya Educational Trust (R.)
Vakwady, Kundapura - 576 257

Ph : 08251 - 289999

SHRI GAJANANA ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

ISHWARAMANGALA - 574313, PUTTUR D. K. KARNATAKA

(Sponsored by : VIVEKANANDA VIDYAVARDHAKA SANGHA, PUTTUR (R.)

Recogn. No : No. C8 (2) ಶಾ. ಶಿ. ಅ. ಹೊ. ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ : 203 : 2008-09 Date : 09-06-2009

School Code : G.G. - 0449 Date : 27-08-2011

Ref No.:

Date : 12/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is certify that **Kum. Shubhashree B** from college of education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 51 days on our esteemed institution from **07-03-2021 to 29-07-2021** and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

Headmaster

HEAD MASTER

Shri Gajanana English Medium High
School, Ishwaramangala - 574 313

MORARJI DESAI RESIDENTIAL SCHOOL MUNDAJE-574228

BELTHANGADI TALUK, DAKSHINA KANNADA

Email: kreismdrs138@gmail.com

Date :25.08.2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

BSU19ED175

This is to certify that **Miss Shwetha.A.S** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 41 days on our esteemed institution from 12/03/2021 to 23/04/2021 and 17/08/2021 to 25/08/2021 and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Principal
Morarji Desai Residential School,
Mundaje, Belthangady Tq.
Dakshina Kannada -574228

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

ATTENDANCE SHEET FOR INTERNSHIP STUDENTS

NAME OF THE STUDENT : SHWETHA.K.S.

NAME OF THE SCHOOL : ಎ. ಕೆ.ಐ.ಐ.ಐ.ಎಂ. ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ ಶಾಲೆ, ಕೋಡಲಹಳ್ಳಿ

SL. No. of WORKING DAYS	DATE	SIGNATURE	SL. NO. OF WORKING DAYS	DATE	SIGNATURE
1.	10/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	15	27/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
	11/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>		Signature of the HM	<u>J.R.S</u>
2.	12/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>		28/03/2021	Sunday
3.	13/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	16.	29/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
	Signature of the HM.	<u>J.R.S</u>	17.	30/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
	14/03/2021	vacant	18.	31/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
4.	15/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	19.	01/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
5.	16/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>		02/04/2021	Good Friday
6.	17/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	20	03/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
7.	18/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>		Signature of the H.M.	<u>J.R.S</u>
8.	19/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	21	04/04/2021	Sunday
9.	20/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	22.	05/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
	Signature of the H.M.	<u>J.R.S</u>	23	06/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
	21/03/2021	vacant	24	07/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
10.	22/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	25	08/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
11.	23/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>	26	09/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
12.	24/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>		10/04/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>
13.	25/03/2021	<u>Shwetha</u>		Signature of the H.M.	<u>J.R.S</u>

27	12/04/2021	Bullt.
	13/04/2021	ಅಜ್ಜಿ
28	14/04/2021	Bullt.
29	15/04/2021	Bullt.
30	16/04/2021	Bullt.
31	17/04/2021	Bullt.
	Signature of the H.M.	J.R.R.
	18/04/2021	Sunday
32	19/04/2021	Bullt.
33	20/04/2021	Bullt.
34	21/04/2021	Bullt.
35	22/04/2021	Bullt.
36	23/04/2021	Bullt.
37	24/04/2021	Bullt.
	Signature of the H.M.	J.R.R.

J. R. R. RAJENDRA
 ಮುಖ್ಯಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು
 ದ. ಕೆ. ಜಿ. ಪಂ. ಹಿ. ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ, ಕೋಡಪವು
 ಉಪ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕನವು - 574 222
 - ಬಂದ್ವಾಳು ತಾಲೂಕು, ದ. ಕೆ.
 Ph: 9741131059

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರ
ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಇಲಾಖೆ

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ.ಪ್ರಾ.ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕಬಕ, ಪುತ್ತೂರುತಾ, ದ.ಕ.ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ

ಇಮೇಲ್‌ನಾಸ:ghskabaka@yahoo.com

ದೂರವಾಣಿ : 0825128118

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms.Shwetha.T from college of education Srinivas University has completed the internship of 60 days on our esteemed institution from 15.03.2021 to 27.07.2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

DATE:13.07.2021

PLACE: KABAKA

ಹಿರಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಧೀಕಾರ ಸಹಾಯಕರು
ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪದವಿ ಪೂರ್ವ ಕಾಲೇಜು
ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕಬಕ
ಪುತ್ತೂರು, ದ. ಕ. 574 220

ಮಿಲಾಗ್ರಿಸ್ ಪದವಿಪೂರ್ವಕಾಲೇಜು

(ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲಾ ವಿಭಾಗ) ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575 001 (ದ.ಕ.)

MILAGRES PRE- UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

(High School Section) MANGALORE - 575001 (D.K.)

ದೂರವಾಣಿ Phone : 0824 - 2425175

Date: 17-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that MRS. SLANI ANISHA LOBO from College of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 50 days in our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 26-04-2021 and from 26-07-2021 to 16-08-2021. Her performance was found to be good.

Signature

VICE PRINCIPAL
MILAGRES PRE-UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
MANGALORE - 575 001

Place : Mangaluru

Date : 17-08-2021

SHARADA VIDYANIKETHANA PUBLIC SCHOOL
DEVINAGARA, TALAPADY, MANGALORE, D.K.

Ph. No. 0824-2280330, 2281220, 9353909330

Email.: svps@sharadagroup.in

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. SMRUTHI A**, pursuing B.Ed in Srinivas College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore is going to complete her internship of 50 days from 08th March 2021 to 15th Sept 2021.

During the aforesaid period her performance is satisfactory.

Thanks & Regards,

PRINCIPAL

PRINCIPAL

Sharada Vidyanikethana Public School
Devi Naqara, Talapady Post, Mangalore-575022

ಸಂತ ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಾ ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ

ಫಿಲೋನಗರ, ಅಂಚೆ : ದರ್ಬೆ 574202, ಪುತ್ತೂರು, ದ.ಕ.

ಮಾನ್ಯತೆ ಆದೇಶ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ : D3/ARR/23/2019-20 DATED 20-11-2019

ಉಪನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು (ಆಡಳಿತ) ಸಾ. ಶಿ. ಇಲಾಖೆ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು 08251 230470

ಡೈಸ್.ಕೋಡ್: 29240408703

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

85U19ED181.

This is to certify that **Ms. SNEHA D GHATE** from college of education, **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has completed the internship of **70 days** on our esteemed institution from **12-03-2021** to **30-08-2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Leonille Vargas

Headmistress

ಸಂತ ಫಿಲೋಮಿನಾ ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಪ್ರೌಢಶಾಲೆ
ಫಿಲೋನಗರ, ದರ್ಬೆ ಅಂಚೆ, ಪುತ್ತೂರು
ದ.ಕ. 574 202, Ph: 230470

Place: Puttur

Date: 31/08/2021

FATHIMA U. P. SCHOOL

P. O. PARIYAPURAM - 679321
VIA. ANGADIPPURAM, Ph: 04933 253131

Date : 14/06/2021.....

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Sonia K George from Fathima UP School Pariyapuram, has completed the internship from 09-03-2021 to Forty five days from our school and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

Head Master
Fathima U.P. School
Pariyapuram

HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

Madani Ground, Ullal-575 020 Mangluru D.K.

Ph: 0824-2461150

Ref.

Date: 23/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **SOUBHAGYA M** from college of education Srinivas University has completed the intership of 58 days on our esteemed institution from 10/3/2021 to 31/7/2021 and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

Handwritten signature and date: 23/08/2021
HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI
English Medium High School
Madani Ground, Ullal - 575 020

12/4/2021	Soumya CB		18/05/2021	
13/4/2021	Soumya CB		19/05/2021	
14/4/2021	Soumya B		20/05/2021	
15/4/2021	Soumya CB		21/05/2021	
16/4/2021	—		22/05/2021	—
17/4/2021	—		23/05/2021	—
			24/05/2021	—

The student teacher of Srinivas College of Education has attended the school for her B.Ed internship for the above mentioned period. She has conducted only one class for 8th std - I Lang. English - grammar. She was asked to prepare well for the class.

B.Ed student Soumya K.B has submitted 5 Eng & 5 Social lesson plans to Co-operative teacher on 28/7/2021.

HM
28/7/2021
Headmaster
PADUA HIGH SCHOOL
MANGALURU - 575 004. D. K.

**D.K.Z.P.H.P SCHOOL, BOLAR
P.O. BOLAR. MANGALORE TALUK 575001**

12-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Ms. Sulatha from college of education. Srinivas University has completed the internship of 80 days on our esteemed institution from 15.03.2021 to 12.08.2021 and the performance was found to be Satisfactory.

ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು
ದ.ಕ. ಜಿ.ಪಂ. ಒ.ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ
ಬೋಲಾರ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು - 575001

**D.K. Z.P.H.P. SCHOOL, VALACHILL
P.O FARANGIPETE, MANGALURU TALUK- 574143**

31.08.2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Sumitha S Kulal** from college of education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 80 days on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021** to **31.08.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Shayara
ಸುಮಿತ್ಥಾ ಕುಲಾಲ್
ವ.ಕ.ಜಿ.ಪ.ಸಿ.ಪ್ರಾ.ಶಾಲೆ
ವಲಚಿಲ್ಲ, P.O:ಫರಂಗಿಪೇಟೆ
ಮಂಗಳೂರು ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು-574143

VITTAL JAYCEES ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL

(Nursery, Primary & High School)

Basavanagudi, Vittal, Bantwal Taluk, D.K. - 574 243

Ph.: (08255) 239070, 265870

E-mail : vjems.school@gmail.com Website : www.vjems.blogspot.com

Sponsored by : VITTAL JAYCEES EDUCATION SOCIETY (REGD.)

Date
25-08-2021

IMMERSION COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that

85419ED186

Mrs/Mr. **SUSHMA** from **College of Education, Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 46 days in our esteemed educational institution/ school from **15-03-2021** to **24-08-2021** and the performance was found to be ~~good~~/Satisfactory/Very good.

Headmaster
V.J.E.M. SCHOOL
VITTAL, D.K.

B M HIGH SCHOOL, ULLAL

ULLAL – 575 020 – D.K. MANGALURU. MOBILE NO: 9880147030

DATE : 23-08-2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Sushmitha S. From college of Education, Srinivas University has completed the internship of 100 days in our institution from 15/03/2021 to 03/08/2021 and the performance was found to be very good.

Principal

Jsoans

ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಬಿ. ಎಂ. ಹೈ.ಸ್ಕೂಲರು
ಉಲ್ಲಾಲ್ - 575 020

**JANATHA HIGHER PRIMARY ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL
ADYANADKA ,KEPU,BANTWALA TALUKU-574260**

School Dis - 29240103612

Adyanadka Educational Society Reg.

Date..23/08/2021

TO WHOM SOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

**This is to certify that SWATHI B from college of
Education Srinivas University has completed the internship of 62
Days on our esteemed institution from 10-03-2021 to 15-08-2021
And the performance was found to be very good.**

**Headmaster
Janatha Higher Primary
English Medium School
Adyanadka, Bantwal Tq. - 574 260, D.K.**

HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI ENGLISH MEDIUM HIGH SCHOOL

Madani Ground, Ullal-575 020 Mangluru D.K.

Ph: 0824-2461150

Ref.

Date: 23/08/2021

TO WHOMSOEVER SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **VARSHA KV** from college of education Srinivas University has completed the intership of 58 days on our esteemed institution from 10/3/2021 to 31/7/2021 and the performance was found to be satisfactory.

Admission
HAZRATH SEYYID MADANI
English Medium High School
Madani Ground, Ullal - 575 020
23/08/2021

SCHOOL REGD. NO. 0082

☎ : 2441866

KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL

Recognised by Karnataka Government

TELECOM HOUSE ROAD, MANGALORE - 575 001

E-Mail ID : ksem2013@gmail.com

19.08.2021

Ref. No. :

Date :

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mrs. J. Vennila Sucila from college of Education, **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has completed the internship of 55 days on our esteemed institution from 10.03.2021 to 06.08.2021 and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

J. Vennila
Headmistress
KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL
OLD KENT ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001
24/08/21

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಮಾದರಿ ಹಿರಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಶಾಲೆ, ಗುತ್ತಿಗಾರು

ಸುಳ್ಯ ತಾಲೂಕು ದ.ಕ. - 574218

Ref

Date : 03-08-2021

ಸೇವಿಸುವ ಶಾಲೆಗೆ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲೆಕ್ಟಿವ್ ಇನ್ಟರ್ನ್ಶಿಪ್ ೨೨. ಇಡಿ
 ತರಗತಿ ಹಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪೂರ್ತಿ ಅವಧಿ ಕೆ ಇವರು
 ದಿನಾಂಕ 10-03-2021 ರಿಂದ 23-07-2021 ರವರೆಗೆ
 ನಮ್ಮ ಶಂಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ 50 ದಿನಗಳ ಕಾಲ ಇಂಟರ್ನ್ಶಿಪ್
 ಅಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಇತ್ಯೇಕಿಯಾಗಿ ಕೆಲವು ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎಂದು
 ಈ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎಂದು ಈ ಮೂಲಕ
 ದೃಢೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ.

ಪದವಿಧರೇತರ ಮುಖ್ಯೋಪಾಧ್ಯಾಯರು
 ಸ. ಮಾ. ಹಿ. ಪ್ರಾ. ಶಾಲೆ, ಗುತ್ತಿಗಾರು
 ಅಂಚೆ: ಗುತ್ತಿಗಾರು, ಸುಳ್ಯ, ದ.ಕ.

☎: 2441866
Mob : 8722964438

KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL

TELECOM HOUSE ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001
DISE Code: 29240610708

6.08.2021

Ref. No. :

Date :

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **MR. WANTEIMI YMBON** from college of Education, **Srinivas University** has completed the internship of 54 days on our esteemed institution from **10.03.2021** to **3.08.2021** and the performance was found to be **Satisfactory**.

Alkhal
Headmistress
KERALA SAMAJAM ENGLISH HIGH SCHOOL
OLD KENT ROAD, MANGALURU - 575 001